

PROBLEMS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN GANJAM DISTRICT OF ODISHA

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Abstract

Teachers are the cornerstone of the whole education system, and the success of education heavily depends on the quality and effectiveness of teachers. The present investigation aimed at studying the financial, administrative, academic, and personal problems faced by secondary school teachers of Ganjam district. A sample of 60 secondary school teachers working in Government High Schools of Ganjam district participated in this study. Data were collected by a self-developed questionnaire and analyzed using frequency and percentage. The findings revealed that, despite having a good salary, teachers face financial difficulties due to the rising cost of living. Over administrative workload created a major distraction for teaching and affected adversely the work life balance. The study also revealed nonacademic duties, lack of subject-related training, lack of access to technology, resistance from students in implementing modern teaching techniques, and limited knowledge of ICT contributed as the major academic problems.

Key words: *Problems, Secondary School Teachers*

Introduction

Education is a core human value that distinguishes people from other living beings. Its vision is to develop the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values of learners through effective teaching and learning processes. In this process, the role of teachers is crucial in shaping the future of students and relates to the goal of education with national development. The success of any educational system depends upon the quality of teachers and that can't be replaced with any other materials. The quality of education improves significantly through the efforts of

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teachers. It can be ensured only when teachers are satisfied, committed, and motivated to serve the interests of students and the wider community (Swain, 2013). The National Education Policy 2020 of India, places significant emphasis on teachers' professional development as a key factor for improving the quality education and the need for continuous professional development of teachers throughout their careers (Subudhi & Rabha, 2025). In this concern for the whole education system, secondary school teachers play an important role in both inside and outside of the schools as they prepare students to become responsible and effective citizens for the country and work as social agent to bring out desirable change in the society (Chopra, 2018). In the current scenario, the expectation from teachers is high, but less attention is given to their problems. Secondary school teachers face multifaceted problems, including professional and personal problems that create a barrier in maintaining their role effectively and give them unsatisfactory job experience. So, it is required to study what kind of problems the secondary school teachers are facing.

The study by Singh and Joshi (2025) revealed that there was a significant negative relationship between teaching competency and occupational of secondary school teachers and recommends measures to decrease teachers' occupational stress and enhance teaching competency. Bhattacharjya and Choudhuri (2024) concluded that there was a weak negative correlation between the occupational stress and job satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers, suggesting that increased stress tended to reduce satisfaction. Matemba (2024) in a study found that secondary school teachers faced several challenges due to low salary, poor working condition, delayed promotion, shortage of teaching learning materials, Lack of students' readiness to learn, poor cooperation between teachers and employers and Influence of politics in education. Pandey and Mukherjee (2023) conducted a study to evaluate the level of occupational stress among secondary school teachers and explored its variations across demographic factors. The findings showed that there was no significant difference in stress levels based on gender or school location and highlighted that workload, role ambiguity, and lack of motivation were key contributors to stress. Suham and Tok (2023) in a study found that government secondary school teachers faced dissatisfaction due to lack of infrastructural facilities and accommodation, inadequate safe drinking water facilities, overcrowded classrooms and overburden of administrative tasks. The studies cited above revealed that hardly any study has been conducted on the problems of secondary school teachers in Ganjam district of Odisha. Hence, studying this research is desirable.

As per NEP 2020, the place of teacher is at centre for fundamental reforms in the whole education system. Their responsibilities are not only confined to educational institutions but also extended to society. Among all levels, secondary education plays a crucial role in the development of learners as it is a bridge between primary and higher education levels. In this stage, secondary school teachers have a great responsibility in guiding the adolescence learners and in maintaining the quality of the teaching learning process. To perform their role and responsibilities effectively, they need a stress-free and supportive work environment. For these their professional and personal problems need to be addressed. Therefore, the investigator has undertaken the present study to identify the financial, administrative, academic, and personal problems faced by the secondary school teachers. The results of the study may help the policy makers, educational administrators, and educational planners to make appropriate measures to support the teachers and to enhance the quality of secondary education.

Research Questions

1. What are the financial problems faced by secondary school teachers?
2. What are the administrative problems faced by secondary school teachers?
3. What are the academic problems faced by secondary school teachers?
4. What are the personal problems faced by secondary school teachers?

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the financial problems of secondary school teachers.
2. To study the administrative problems of secondary school teachers.
3. To study the academic problems of secondary school teachers.
4. To study the personal problems of secondary school teachers.

Methodology

As the objective of the present study was to explore the problems of secondary school teachers, **Descriptive Survey Method** was used.

Sample: A sample of 60 secondary school teachers from 11 Government Secondary Schools situated in the Rangeilunda block of Ganjam district consisted of the sample of the study. Among the selected samples, 25 were male and 35 were female. Investigators used purposive sampling technique for the selection of the sample.

Tool

The following tool was developed and used by the investigator for the purpose of data collection:

a. Questionnaire for Secondary School Teachers

Main Findings

The following are the main findings of the present study

- Majority of secondary school teachers of Ganjam district (76.67%) expressed satisfaction with their salary.
- Despite being satisfied with their salary, many teachers (93.33%) strongly gave their views in favour of revision of the existing pay scale to match that of Central Government employees.
- About the financial difficulties faced by teachers, the rising cost of living was the most common concern, along with lack of allowances and personal loan burdens. This suggests that teachers' financial stress was mainly due to outside economic pressures rather than just their salary.
- It was found that 75% of teachers perceived themselves financially stable as compared to other professions.
- More than 11% of teachers recommended revision of the pay scale like Central govt. employees and suggested for restoring an old pension scheme.
- More than 66.67% of teachers felt overburdened due to administrative duties and stated that these tasks often distracted them from their main teaching work.
- More than 86% of teachers reported that administrative responsibilities often extended beyond regular school hours, making it harder to balance work with family and personal time.
- Most teachers (60%) suggested appointing non-teaching staff as the best way to reduce the administrative workload. More than 60% of teachers recommended clearer guidelines for administrative duties and providing administrative support training to help teachers handle these responsibilities more effectively.
- The study revealed that non-academic duties added significant stress to teachers' academic work. The teachers felt that handling tasks that are not related to teaching increased their workload and made academic responsibilities difficult.
- More than 18% of teachers pointed out that insufficient training, lack of access to technology, and resistance from students were the difficulties in implementing modern teaching techniques.

- Academic challenges influenced teachers' job satisfaction. Some teachers (30%) felt that these challenges reduced their satisfaction significantly.
- Majority of teachers (61.67%) opined that workload due to non-academic work was the biggest barrier to managing academic activities effectively. About 15% of teachers faced challenges as students lacked age-appropriate knowledge. Further, 16.67% of teachers mentioned that frequent training sessions also contributed to their workload.
- The study revealed that excessive workload emerged as the main challenge that hindered teachers' motivation in their work.
- The findings showed that personal relationships with colleagues played an important role in shaping the professional environment. Teachers felt that these relationships helped to create a positive work atmosphere and encouraged teamwork.
- Despite personal challenges, teachers were able to keep their professional responsibilities steady and found strength and motivation through supportive relationships at work.
- More than 22% of teachers faced difficulties such as lack of subject-related training, work pressure from non-academic duties, and limited knowledge of ICT.
- Teachers suggested for improving their professional status through professional development activities and training, appointing non-teaching staff to reduce workload, better financial support, transportation and accommodation facilities and stronger supervision from school leaders to create a more supportive teaching environment.

Educational implications

The present study examined the financial, administrative, academic, and personal problems faced by secondary school teachers of Ganjam district. The following suggestions may be taken into consideration for solving the problems of teachers.

- There is a need for revision of the pay scale of secondary school teachers like Central Government employees.
- There is a need to introduce additional allowances for teachers due to rising cost of living, to ease external economic pressures on teachers.
- Efforts should be made to provide better transportation facilities, accommodation facilities and welfare benefits for teachers working in both urban and rural areas to enhance their overall financial well-being.

- Schools should appoint an adequate number of non-teaching staff to handle administrative work, allowing teachers to focus on instructional duties.
- Teachers should be given administrative management training so that they can handle necessary administrative responsibilities more efficiently with less stress.
- Regular dialogue between teachers and administrators can help to identify and address specific administrative burdens that disrupt classroom teaching and teacher satisfaction.
- Schools should invest in ICT infrastructure for easy access to digital tools and resources, especially in under-resourced areas.
- Professional development programmes must be responsive to teachers' needs, with targeted support on classroom management strategies and handling student diversity.
- Educational authorities should promote a supportive and collaborative work culture in schools.

The findings of the present study conclude that secondary school teachers faced financial difficulties due to rising cost of living, which is due to outside economic pressure and lack of allowances. Most teachers feel overburden because of administrative duties which often distract them from teaching and these responsibilities also hamper the work-life balance. For the solution to these problems many teachers suggested for appointment of non-teaching staff and to bring out a clear guideline for administrative duties, which helps to eradicate this problem. The secondary school teachers also face academic challenges due to lack of subject-related training, lack of access to technology, resistance from students in implementing modern teaching techniques, and limited knowledge of ICT. This study gives a clear scenario of financial, administrative, academic, and personal problems faced by the secondary school teachers of Ganjam district with their suggestions for improvement of the teachers.

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